

This is a preprint, author-produced PDF of an article accepted for publication in the American Journal of Psychiatry following peer review and allowed to be disseminated under AJP policy. The definitive publisher-authenticated version is: Scheeringa MS (2024). Clarifying confounder variables and cross-sectional power to make causal conclusions about race, adversity, and brain differences. American Journal of Psychiatry, February 2024, 181, 2, 166-167, doi: 10.1176/appi.ajp.20230223

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

Title: Clarifying confounder variables and cross-sectional power to make causal conclusions about race, adversity, and brain differences

Michael S. Scheeringa, MD

Professor, Department of Psychiatry and Behavioral Sciences, Tulane University School of Medicine, New Orleans, LA

Disclosure. Dr. Scheeringa receives royalties from Guilford Press and Central Recovery Press.

Acknowledgements: None

TO THE EDITOR: In the February 2023 issue of this journal, Dumornay et al. (2023) reported their effort to understand how differences in volume of brain regions were partially explained by racial differences in exposure to adversity (1). Given the amount of attention given to their extraordinary causal conclusions in an editorial (2), press releases (3, 4, 5), and media coverage (6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11), I believe this paper merits additional examination on several empirical issues. They made three main claims which I argue were not demonstrated.

First, they claimed that differences in brain volumes between Black and White children in eleven of fourteen brain regions were “race-related differences.” The Black and White groups, however, were not equivalent as Black children were significantly worse off than White children on all seven adversity measures. Adversity was therefore a confounder variable because it was significantly related to both predictor (race) and outcome (brain regions).

Statistical control of confounders can only estimate the amount of mathematical variance attributable to confounders, but does not truly measure the impact of confounders. Only study design that controls how individuals are recruited can truly measure the impact of confounders.

They should have performed matching on the adversity variables to create groups of Black and White children that were comparable on adversities. How this got through peer review without matching is a question the editors ought to seriously ponder. Any reviewer should have caught this, but wasn't there a statistical reviewer?

Second, they found that the seven adversities were associated with differences in volumes of 12 of the 14 brain regions and claimed this was a causal relationship, i.e., adversities caused structural brain differences. They failed, however, to emphasize how thin these associations were. Out of 98 tests between seven adversities and 14 brain regions, only 17 were significant.

Most importantly, the brain imaging data was cross-sectional, being collected once per subject at 9-10-years of age. I mention this because neither Dumornay et al. nor the editorial, press releases, or media stories mentioned this rather key issue. Instead they claimed this was evidence of toxic stress, which is the extraordinary theory that stress causes permanent damage to human brains. When pre-trauma prospective studies in humans have been reviewed (and there are now more than two dozen such studies) this theory has failed to be supported (12, 13, 14). Not a trivial point when researchers, editorialists, and journalists are using the study to make profound accusations about systemic racism.

Third, Dumornay et al. found that adversity accounted for some of the mathematical variance between race and brain regions. They claimed that “we have shown that differential exposure to childhood adversity contributes to racial differences between Black American and White American children in gray matter volumes of brain regions key to emotion regulation,” which they claimed was a demonstration of systemic racism on brains. This claim is contingent on their first two claims being true. Since I believe their first and second claims are unsupported, the third claim is also unsupported.

REFERENCES

1. Dumornay NM, Lebois LAM, Ressler KJ, Harnett NG. Racial Disparities in Adversity During Childhood and the False Appearance of Race-Related Differences in Brain Structure. *Am J Psychiatry* 2023; 180(2):127-38
2. Barch DM, Luby JL. Understanding social determinants of brain health during development. *Am J Psychiatry* 2023; 180(2):108-10

3. Racial disparities in childhood adversity linked to brain structural differences in U.S. children [press release]. <https://www.mcleanhospital.org/news/racial-disparities-childhood-adversity-linked-brain-structural-differences-us-children>: McLean Hospital, February 1, 2023
4. Disparities linked to differences in brain structures in U.S. Children [press release]. <https://hms.harvard.edu/news/disparities-linked-differences-brain-structures-us-children>: Harvard University, February 1, 2023 2023
5. Racial disparities in childhood adversity linked to brain structural differences in U.S. children [press release]. <https://www.psychiatry.org/News-room/News-Releases/Racial-Disparities-in-Childhood-Adversity>: American Psychiatric Association, February 1, 2023
6. O'Connor K. Study finds childhood adversity linked to brain differences in White, Black children. *Psychiatr News* [Internet]. [cited 2023 March 19]; February 2, 2023. Available from: <https://psychnews.psychiatryonline.org/doi/10.1176/appi.pn.2023.03.2.7>.
7. Wisdom P. Racial disparities in childhood adversity linked to brain structural differences in US children. *Cognitive Science News* [Internet]. [cited 2023 March 19]; February 1, 2023. Available from: <https://cognitivesciencenews.com/2023/02/01/racial-disparities-in-childhood-adversity-linked-to-brain-structural-differences-in-us-children/>.
8. Volpe KD. Racial disparities linked to altered brain structure in Black children. *The Clinical Advisor* [Internet]. [cited 2023 March 19]; February 24, 2023. Available from: <https://www.clinicaladvisor.com/home/topics/neurology-information-center/racial-disparities-altered-brain-structure-black-children-adversity/>.
9. Richardson R. How does structural racism impact a child's brain? A first-of-its-kind study has the answer[cited 2023 March 19]; February 15, 2023. Available from: <https://www.today.com/health/mind-body/racism-mental-health-black-children-rcna68836>.

10. NBC News. Racial disparities can affect brain development in Black children, new study finds[cited 2023 March 19]; February 2, 2023. Available from: <https://www.nbcnews.com/news/nbcblk/study-racial-disparities-can-affect-brain-development-black-children-rcna68641>.
11. PBS. New study reveals the effect of racism and poverty on children's brains[cited 2023 February 20]; February 18, 2023. Available from: <https://www.pbs.org/newshour/show/new-study-reveals-the-effect-of-racism-and-poverty-on-childrens-brains>.
12. DiGangi JA, Gomez D, Mendoza L, Jason LA, Keys CB, Koenen KC. Pretrauma risk factors for posttraumatic stress disorder: A systematic review of the literature. *Clin Psychol Rev* 2013; 33:728-44
13. Danese A, Moffitt TE, Arseneault L, Bleiberg BA, Dinardo PB, Gandelman SB, et al. The origins of cognitive deficits in victimized children: Implications for neuroscientists and clinicians. *Am J Psychiatry* 2017; 174:349-61
14. Scheeringa MS. Reexamination of diathesis stress and neurotoxic stress theories: A qualitative review of pre-trauma neurobiology in relation to posttraumatic stress symptoms. *Int J Methods Psychiatr Res* 2020;